

Autonomous Drugs Optimal Management, Part III: Electrode-Tip Temperature Control in Radiofrequency Ablation for Breast Cancer using D-P and First Order Compensators Compared with a PID Controller

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 12th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Electrode-tip temperature Breast Cancer treatment using RFA PID controller D-P compensator First-order compensator</p>	<p>This is the third research paper in a series aiming at investigating the autonomous drugs optimal management. It handles the control of the electrode-tip of the radiofrequency ablation system to increase the efficacy of the tumor ablation of females-breast cancer. Two control compensators are proposed to control the electrode tip and a simulation data for 20 V input from a 2020 research paper is addressed to find a reasonable transfer function model for this process. The proposed compensators (D-P and first-order) are tuned and analyzed in a single control-loop with the RFA electrode for the step time response for a specific desired tip temperature tracking and compared with using a PID controller tuned by the authors. The best controller/compensator is assigned and its robustness is checked.</p>

1. Introduction

Radiofrequency ablation is a technique having the characteristic of minimal invasive therapy and hence became an alternative to the standard surgical resection treatment of human breast cancer with tumors ≤ 20 mm [1]-[4]. One of the main parameters in radiofrequency ablation is the temperature of its electrode-tip where it has a direct effect on the ablation efficacy in destroying the tumor cells [5]-[7]. Because of this, the main objective of this research paper is to investigate the use of efficient two control compensators from the second generation introduced by professor Galal Hassaan (the first author of the present work) since 2014 to achieve fast time response without any overshoot, undershoot or steady-state error with comparison with using a PID controller from the first generation of PID controllers.

2. Literature Review

Extrand et al. (2005) investigated the preferential heating of breast tumors due to the surrounding of the tumor with fat. They showed experimentally that the breast tissue showed a preferential heating of the tumor which was supported by computer simulations based on finite elements models [8]. Quaranta et al. (2007) evaluated the efficacy of single-needle cool-tip RF breast ablation in terms of temperature distribution and procedure duration compared to multiprobe RF ablation. They concluded that the proposed col-tip RF breast ablation might kill more tumor cells than the multiprobe ablation technique [7]. Habibi et al. (2008) evaluated the intralesional injection of IL-7 and IL-15 in RF thermal ablation treated murine tumor using two different breast carcinoma models. They showed that RF thermal ablation combined with the administration of IL-7 and IL-15 after RFA inhibited tumor development, lung metastasis and reduced the myeloid derived suppressor cells [10]. Rubio, Vera and Leija (2013) outlined that breast cancer is most common type of cancer among women and defined the 'thermal therapy' as a type cancer treatment in which body tissue is exposed to high temperatures. They also defined the high temperature 'hyperthermia' as the direct application of thermal therapies to a tumor to achieve substantial tumor destruction. They used numerical electromagnetic and thermal simulations to optimize the electrode design and predict the heating pattern [11].

Singh and Repaka (2016) outlined that RFA is the most promising and widely applied technique in clinical practice for the local treatment of solid tumors and its application in the treatment of breast cancer was in its developing stage. They analyzed the efficacy of temperature-controlled RFA in breast tumor with different target temperatures. They use a closed-loop feedback PID controller performing a temperature-controlled RFA. They concluded that the finite element method revealed a strong dependence of the ablation volume on the target temperature during RFA [5]. Lopez et al. (2010) explored the variations of temperature

distribution and coagulation zone size computed by a two-compartment RFA model including reversible changes in tissue conductivity due to temperature and irreversible changes due to thermal coagulation. They concluded that irreversible changes in the tissue conductivity did not have a significant effect on the coagulation zone in two-compartment RFA models [12]. Miaskowski and Gas (2023) presented a comparative analysis of the specific absorption rate and temperature distribution during RFA for different female breast tumors. They considered four tumor-models for irregular tumor with RF electrode with a specific voltage and 100 kHz frequency. They determined the specific ablation rate inside the tumors with the temperature profile [13]. Futamura et al. (2025) outlined that RFA is a minimally invasive technique employed in the management of small breast tumors delivering a high frequency current to a needle electrode. They evaluated ablation temperature, time and impedance according to breast density. They concluded that breast density should be considered to plan the RFA parameters for optimal treatment efficacy [14].

3. The Controlled Electrode-tip Temperature as a Process

Paruch investigated the mathematical modeling of Brist tumor destruction using heating during radiofrequency ablation [15]. They presented a set of temperature profiles for RFA input voltages of 10, 12.5, 15, 17.5 and 20 V simulated for a breast cancer plotted for time span up to 10 minutes. A higher electrode-tip temperature of 81 °C was obtained with 20 V input voltage. For sake of investigating the design and tuning of compensators/controllers for the control of the electrode-tip temperature to a pre-assigned value for optimum operation of the RFA process, a transfer function model has to be identified. We have chosen the electrode temperature profile at 20 V input voltage for this purpose. Within the 10 minutes span of Paruch-temperature profiles, it was obvious that there is no steady-state value which means that the process is unstable. The best model representing the temperature change profile (referenced to a starting temperature of 25 °C of Paruch data was integrated-1/2 orders model without time delay for the electrode-temperature process transfer function $G_p(s)$ given by:

$$G_p(s) = K_p(T_{zp}s + 1)/[s(T_{1p}s + 1)(T_{2p}s + 1)] \tag{1}$$

Where: K_p is the process gain, T_{zp} is the time constant of the process zero, T_{1p} and T_{2p} are time constants of the process simple poles.

The Integral of square error (ISE) performance index [16] is used through minimization to identify the four process parameters using the MATLAB optimization toolbox [17]. The identified parameters of the transfer function model in Eq.1 are given below with 0.9984 correlation coefficient:

$$K_p = 0.00335, T_{zp} = 293.0825, T_{1p} = 15.9959, T_{2p} = 15.9959 \tag{2}$$

The electrode-tip temperature profile for 20 V input using Paruch simulation and the present identified transfer function model is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Electrode-tip temperature change of a RFA of a breast tumor.

4. Controlling the Electrode-tip Temperature using a PID Controller

The PID controller is one of the first generation of PID controllers originated in 1922 with theoretical analysis and applied to ship control [18]. We start here by a PID controller for sake of comparison with control compensators from the second generation presented by Dr. Galal Hassaan in 2014 [19],[20]. The transfer function of the PID controller is given by [21]:

$$G_{c1}(s) = K_{pc1} + \left(\frac{K_{i1}}{s}\right) + K_{d1}s \tag{3}$$

The PID controller has three gain parameters to be tuned for good closed-loop control performance. The ITAE performance index [22] is minimized using the MATLAB optimization toolbox [17] and produced the following tuned PID gain coefficients:

$$K_{pc1} = 1.250, K_{i1} = 0.01907, K_{d1} = 0.0979 \tag{4}$$

It was reported that the optimal electrode-tip temperature for an efficient RFA of early breast tumor is from 64 to 100 °C [23]. In all the investigated controller and compensators in the present work we have selected 95 °C as a desired electrode-tip temperature (70 °C change from the origin 25 °C value of Paruch work [15]). The Electrode-tip temperature process model in Eq.1 with parameters in Eq.2 and the PID controller transfer function in Eq.3 with gain parameters in Eq.4 are used to plot the step time

response of the closed-loop control system for a 70 °C desired electrode temperature change is generated using MATLAB [24] and shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2: PID controller-controlled electrode-tip temperature.

Comments:

- Maximum percentage overshoot: 7.273 %
- Settling time to ± 2 % tolerance: 762.23 s
- Rise time: 84.4 s
- Steady-state error: zero

5. Controlling the Electrode-tip Temperature using a D-P Compensator

The DP compensator is one of the second generation of control compensators introduced by Prof. Galal Hassaan in 2025 [25]. It is composed of two control elements: the first is a derivative control mode (D-control mode) set in the feedforward path of a single-loop control block diagram just after the error detector and the second is a proportional control mode (P-control mode) set in the feedback path feeding its output to the error detector. It has the transfer functions $G_{c21}(s)$ and $G_{c22}(s)$ given by:

$$G_{c21}(s) = K_{d2}s, \quad G_{c22}(s) = K_{pc2} \tag{5}$$

The D-P compensator has two gain parameters K_{d2} and K_{pc2} to be tuned for good performance for the closed-loop control system for the RFA electrode-tip temperature. The D-P compensator is tuned as follows:

- The transfer function is derived using the compensator transfer functions in Eq.5 and the process transfer function in Eq.1.
- For a zero steady-state error (where the output electrode-tip temperature converges to the desired value), the free terms in the closed-loop transfer numerator and denominator have to be equal providing the following condition relating the compensator gain parameters:

$$K_{d2} = 1/(K_p - K_p K_{pc2}) \tag{6}$$

- Now, the closed-loop transfer function will be function only of the compensator gain K_{pc2} while K_{d2} will be assigned using Eq.6.
- The ITAE performance index [22] is minimized using the MATLAB optimization toolbox [17] producing with Eq.6 the following tuned gain parameters of the D-P compensator:

$$K_{pc2} = 2532.322, \quad K_{d2} = 0.4394 \tag{7}$$

Now, with the optimal controller gain parameters assigned, the step time response of the control system for a desired electrode-tip temperature of 95 oC (70 oC temperature change) is generated using the MATLAB ‘step’ command [24] and shown in Fig.3.

Comments:

- Maximum percentage overshoot: zero (compared with 7.273 % for a PID controller).
- Settling time to ± 2 % tolerance: 1.904 s (compared with 762.23 s for a PID controller).
- Rise time: 1.074 s (compared with 84.4 s for a PID controller).
- Steady-state error: zero

Figure 3: D-P compensator-controlled electrode-tip temperature.

The D-P compensator is providing wonderful control system performance measures in the time domain. But, is it robust with respect the compensator parameters change? To answer this question, we considered the change of K_{pc2} as follows:

- A K_{pc2} value of 0.42 with 4.415 % decrease from the optimal value of 0.4394.
- A K_{pc2} value of 0.45 with 2.412 % increase from the optimal value of 0.4394.

The effect of this variation in K_{pc2} is shown graphically in Fig.4. The time-based characteristics of the D-P controlled temperature process is presented in Table 1.

Figure 4: Effect of the D-P compensator proportional gain on the electrode-tip temperature.

Table 1: D-P Compensator based Characteristics of the Electrode-tip Temperature Control System.

K_{pc2}	0.4394	0.42	0.45
OS_{max}	0	0	0
(%)			
T_s (s)	1.904	2.000	2.917
T_r (s)	1.074	1.011	1.120
e_{ss} (°C)	0	-2.485	1.268

OS_{max} : Maximum percentage overshoot.

T_s : Settling time to 2 % tolerance.

T_r : Rise time.

e_{ss} : Steady-state error.

Comments:

- The control system was still stable.
- It did not overshoot nor undershoot.
- The settling time change was within one s.

- The rise time change was within 0.063 s.
- The steady-state error was within 2.485 °C (within the optimal range of the RFA electrode-tip temperature).
- Therefore. We can say that the D-P compensator is *ROBUST* with respect to its parameters change within 4.4 %.

6. Controlling the Electrode-tip Temperature using a First-order Compensator

The First-order compensator is one of the first generation of control compensators introduced during the second half of the 21st century [26]. It was used by Prof. Galal Hassaan for the control of different processes using different forms of the compensator between 2014-2021 [27]-[29]. The transfer function $G_{c3}(s)$ of the first-order compensator is given by [27]:

$$G_{c3}(s) = K_{c3}(T_{z3}s + 1)/(T_{p3}s + 1) \tag{8}$$

The first-order compensator has three parameters K_{c3} (compensator gain), T_{z3} (simple zero time constant) and T_{p3} (simple pole time constant) to be tuned for good performance for the closed-loop control system for the RFA electrode-tip temperature. The first-order compensator is tuned as follows:

- The open-loop transfer function $G_{c3}(s)G_p(s)$ is derived by multiplying the compensator transfer function in Eq.8 and the process transfer function in Eq.1.
- The zero/pole cancellation technique [30] is used to cancel the compensator zero with one of the process simple poles and the pole of the compensator with the zero of the process revealing:

$$T_{z3} = 15.9959 \text{ s} , T_{p3} = 293.0825 \text{ s} \tag{9}$$

- With the time constants in Eq.9, the transfer function of the control system incorporating the first-order compensator and the electrode-tip temperature process will be a standard second-order one.
- A critical damping condition is selected to avoid maximum overshoot and provide a dynamic control system with minimum settling time. This condition reveals directly the compensator gain K_{c3} as:

$$K_{c3} = 4.66398 \tag{10}$$

Using the closed-loop transfer function of the single-loop block diagram of the proposed control system and the first-order compensator tuned parameters in Eqs.9 and 10, the step time response of the control system is drawn for a desired electrode-tip temperature change of 70 °C and shown in Fig.5 using the ‘step’ and ‘plot’ command of MATLAB [24].

Figure 5: First-order compensator-controlled electrode-tip temperature.

Comments:

- Maximum percentage overshoot: zero (compared with 7.273 % for a PID controller).
- Settling time to ± 2 % tolerance: 186.64 s (compared with 762.23 s for a PID controller).
- Rise time: 1.074 s (compared with 84.4 s for a PID controller).
- Steady-state error: zero

7. Comparison of the Time-based Characteristics Associated with the Proposed Compensators

The time-based characteristics of the control systems using the D-P and first-order compensators are compared with those when using a PID controller in graphical and table forms. Fig.6 shows a graphical comparison of the step time responses for 70 °C electrode-tip temperature change. Numerically, the comparison is presented in Table 2.

Figure 5: First-order compensator-controlled electrode-tip temperature.

Table 2: Comparison of Time-based Characteristics of the Electrode Temperature Control Systems.

Controller/Compensators	PID Controller	D-P Compensator	First-order Compensator
OS _{max} (%)	7.273	0	0
T _s (s)	762.23	1.904	186.44
T _r (s)	84.40	1.071	1.074
e _{ss} (°C)	0	0	0

8. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1 Summary

Temperature of the RFA electrode-tip has vital importance in the application of RFA to breast cancer treatment for high efficacy and safe operation in relatively small time without destruction of un-tumor tissues. Two compensators, one from the second generation of control compensators (D-P compensator) and one from the first generation (first-order compensator) were selected for this purpose compared with a PID controller from the first generation of PID controllers. The step time response for a specific desired electrode-tip temperature is compared graphically and numerically.

8.2 Conclusion

- The RFA electrode temperature due to an input voltage was an unstable process.
- The electrode temperature process was identified as an integrated-1/2 orders transfer function model.
- The proposed two compensators and the PID controller were tuned for stable control systems and good performance characteristics.
- The tuning procedure was based on satisfying specific characteristics for the step time response of the control system such as zero maximum overshoot and zero steady-state error plus using a specific performance index minimized using MATLAB optimization toolbox.
- The PID controller provided a 7.273 % maximum overshoot compared with zero for the D-P and first-order compensators.
- The PID controller provided a 762.73 s settling time to $\pm 2\%$ tolerance compared with 1.904 s for the D-P compensator and 186.44 s for the first-order compensator.
- The PID controller provided a 84.4 s rise time compared with 1.074 s for both D-P and first-order compensators.
- The PID controller and the two proposed compensators succeeded to eliminate completely the steady-state error giving the highest operational efficacy.
- The D-P compensator was proven to be the best selection to control this unstable temperature process providing the best time-based characteristics.
- The D-P compensator had proven to be a robust control technique with respect to its gain parameters.

8.3 Recommendations

- This is a computer-based simulation analysis.
- Clinical application is required to verify the efficacy of using the D-P compensator as a new technique never used before in cancer treatment.

References

- [1] Ni, Y. et al. (2005). A review of the general aspects of radiofrequency ablation. *Abdominal Imaging*, 39: 381-400.
- [2] Ito, T. et al. (2017). Radiofrequency ablation of breast cancer: a retrospective study. *Clinical Breast Cancer*, 18(4):e495-e500.

- [3] Xia, L., Hu, Q. & Xu, W. (2021). Efficacy and safety of radiofrequency ablation for breast cancer smaller than 2 cm: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers on Oncology*, 11:11 pages.
- [4] Toi, M. et al. (2024). Non-surgical ablation for breast cancer: an emerging therapeutic optimization. *The Lancet oncology*, 25(3):e114-e125.
- [5] Singh, S. & Repaka, R. (2016). Effects of target temperature on ablation volume during temperature-controlled RFA of breast tumor. *The Proceedings of the 2016 COMSOL Conference*, Bangalore, India, 7 pages.
- [6] Wang, X. et al. (2019). Numerical evaluation of ablation zone under different tip temperatures during radiofrequency ablation. *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, 16(4):2514-2531.
- [7] Ahmed, M. S., El-Wakad, M. & Hassan, M. (2023). The effect of thermal and electrical conductivities on the ablation volume during radiofrequency ablation process. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 14(1):485-493.
- [8] Ekstrand, V. et al. (2005). Influence of electrical and thermal properties on RF ablation of breast cancer: is the tumor preferentially heated?. *Biomedical and Engineering Online*, 4(41):16 pages.
- [9] Quaranta, V. et al. (2007). FEM analysis of RF breast ablation: Multiprobe versus cool-tip electrode. *Anticancer Research*, 27:775-784.
- [10] Habibi, M. et al. (2008). Radiofrequency thermal ablation of breast tumors combined with intralesional administration of IL-7 and IL-15 augments anti-tumor immune responses and inhibits tumor development and metastasis. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*, 114(3):423-431.
- [11] Rubio, M., Vesa, A. & Leija, L. (2013). High temperature hyperthermia in breast cancer treatment, in Huijgol, N. (Editor), *Hyperthermia. InTech*.
- [12] Lopez, D. et al. (2020). Two-compartment mathematical modeling in RF tumor ablation: new insight when irreversible changes in electrical conductivity are considered. *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, 17(6):7980-7993.
- [13] Miaskowski, A. & Gas, P. (2023). Numerical estimation of SAR and temperature distributions inside differently shaped female breast tumors during radiofrequency ablation, *Materials*, 16(223):20 pages.
- [14] Futamura, M. et al. (2025). Impact of breast density on the efficacy of radiofrequency ablation in early-stage breast cancer. *Breast Cancer*:8 pages, DOI:10.1007/s12282-025-01775-7.
- [15] Paruch, M. (2020). Mathematical modeling of breast tumor destructive using fast heating during radiofrequency ablation. *Materials*, 13(136):19 pages.
- [16] Rathore, N., Singh, V. & Chauhan, D. (2015). ISE PID controller tuning for position control of DC servomotor using IJ. *2015 International Conference on Signal Processing, Computers and Control*, September 10-12, India:125-128.
- [17] Lopez, C. P. (2014). MATLAB optimization techniques, *Après*.
- [18] Cahill, J. (2013). PID control history and advancements. *Emerson Automation Experts*, <https://www.emersonautomationexperts.com/2013/control-safety-systems/pid-control-history-and-advancements/>, April 3.
- [19] Hassaan, G. A. (2014). A novel feedback PD compensator used with underdamped second-order processes. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 4(2):10 pages.
- [20] Hassaan, G. A. (2015). Tuning of a novel third-order feedforward compensator, Part I: used with underdamped second-order-like process. *International Journal of Scientific Research Engineering*, 4(5):441-445.
- [21] Benette, S. (2001). The past of PID controllers. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 45:43-53.
- [22] Martins, F. G. (2005). Tuning PID controllers using the ITAE criterion. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 21(5):867-873.
- [23] Ohtani, S. et al. (2011). Radiofrequency ablation of early breast cancer followed by delayed surgical resection- A promising alternative to breast-conserving surgery. *The Breast*, 20:431-436.
- [24] Mathworks (2025). Step- step response of dynamic system, <https://ww2.mathworks.cn/help/ident/ref/dynamicsystem.step.html>
- [25] Hassaan, G. A. (2025). Autonomous human body control, Part XV: Intradialytic hypotension control during hemodialysis using first-order and D-P compensators compared with a PD controller, *International Journal of Computer Techniques*, 12(5):711-719.
- [26] Ogata, K. (2010). Modern control engineering, 5th Edition, *Pearson*:9-10.
- [27] Hassaan, G. A. (2014). Tuning of a first-order lag-lead compensator used with a simple pole plus double integrator process. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science & Technology*, 2(4):17-20.
- [28] Hassaan, G. A. (2015). Tuning of a feedback lag-lead first-order compensator used with a fractional time delay double integrating process. *International Journal of Recent Engineering Science*, 12(6):6 pages.
- [29] Hassaan, G. A. (2021). Tuning of a control compensator from the first generation with comparison with compensators from the second generation. *Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances*, 9(3):38-49.
- [30] Sajnekar, D., Deshpande, D. & Mohril, R. (2013). Comparison of pole placement & pole zero cancellation method for tuning PID controller of a digital excitation control system, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(4):7 pages.
- [31] Mutluel, O. (2023). Al-Kindi from perspective of positive sciences, *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 11(11):57-61.
- [32] Wikipedia (2025). Al-Kindi, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Al-Kindi>, October.

Dedication

Al-Kindi on Iraqi stamp from 1962

YAQUB BIN ISHAQ AL-KINDI [31],[32]

- He was born in Kufa of Iraq in 801 AC and died in Baghdad in 873 AC.
- His research work covered: Logic, ethics, mathematics, physics, chemistry, astronomy, astrology, pharmacology, medicine and geology.
- He wrote more than 30 treatises in medicine.
- He developed a mathematical scale to quantify the 'drug strength'.
- He devised a system helping physicians to know in advance the most critical days of a patient's illness.
- He wrote a treatise about the relationship between astronomy, astrology and medicine.
- He wrote treatises on precious and non-precious stones, metallurgy and sword making.
- He wrote a book about '*chemistry of perfume and distillations*' presenting recipes of 107 kinds of perfumes.
- He wrote treatises on mathematics and optics.
- He wrote a treatise presenting the changes in the human body owing to the rise or fall of its temperature.
- This is why we dedicate this research work to Al-Kindi, the great scientist of the 9th century (Gregorian)